

Difficulties in teaching English to technical students.

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Abstract: All living things have some means of conveying information to others in their group, which is ultimately important for their survival. Some use voice noises, others use physical gestures or facial expressions. Many use different methods.

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Do you find it difficult to use vocabulary words with multiple meanings, have you come across a word that you know (as you think) but is used in a completely strange way? Vocabulary in English is especially difficult because many words have different meanings and can be confused. After all, it's not easy to remember different definitions for each word. Take the word date, for example. The word can refer to a specific day of the month, a time when two people spend romantically with each other, the only way to accurately determine which value is being used is to follow the context. This means that you need to use the surrounding words and phrases to understand which definition of the incomprehensible word is appropriate here.

Even if you don't know the meaning of a difficult word, contextual instructions can help you understand it! Can you determine what the word date means in the following sentences? When is the first day of school again? Would you like to go on a date with me? In the first sentence, someone asks when day school starts. This is not a romantic encounter between the two. The first definition fits here.

The methodology of teaching English, as the builders of the Tower of Babel spoke different languages, the society became in need of interpreters. Interpreters were

appreciated everywhere. Until recently, a foreign language was more of a hobby than a cruel reality. Knowing a foreign language means aesthetics, belonging to a certain circle, or (the most harmless option) - being called eccentric. But times are changing. Any home you know starts with an architectural plan. Now we are increasingly afraid of the huge fortress called the "Foreign Language," at the top of which the flag (mostly English) flutters proudly. And in this case, knowledge of modern teaching methods serves as a necessary plan. Recently, when the education technology market has been filled with suggestions for different methods of learning English, the question "What method do you use to teach?" remains increasingly relevant, indicating that the culture of consuming intellectual products has increased. A confused entrant, student, or business person (including a student) is increasingly stuck in front of language shelves with linguistic literature and media, or thinking of a long list of advertisements. One of the selection criteria is the price, but the main ... "English in two weeks", "Communicative methods of teaching English", "English with English in Moscow", "Effective express method", "English subconscious" degree " finally. So much is new and unknown! And it raises doubts about the results. Can you believe in modern technology? give preference to "brands"? The development and radical changes in language learning methods are undoubtedly related to innovations in the field of individual and group psychology. Now there is a marked change in the minds of the people and in the development of new thinking: the need for self-awareness and understanding, proclaimed by A. Maslow, arises. The psychological factor is gaining a leading position in the study of foreign languages. The authenticity of communication, balanced demands and claims, mutual benefit, respect for the freedom of other people - this is a set of unwritten rules for establishing a constructive relationship in the "teacher-student" system. Fifth, but in no case was the most important element of this system selected. It comes from a student attending a course that best suits his or her needs. In the classroom, the student is no longer limited in his choice of speech tools and specific speech behaviors. The choice of teacher is also not limited: teaching methods and techniques - from games and parts of lessons to simultaneous translation; in the organization of lessons; in the selection of textbooks and study guides - from many local publications to products

from Oxford, Cambridge, London, New York and Sydney. Now the teacher can choose, create, combine, change. The basic technique is truly the most ancient and traditional style. High school students were taught Latin and Greek in exactly the same way, while the French were naturally mastered, with strong suggestions from the governors and communication with Amman and the pope. The classical method, like no other, fits the definition of a “plan to occupy a castle”: phonetic ciphers, visual representations of syntactic constructions, mandatory vocabulary. The student clearly understands: Sir Kalm, Monsieur Gallantri or Herr Sanity, he is: a) willing to spend 2-3 years; b) be patient (learning starts from the beginning); c) I remember the syntax of how topics, affixes can be expressed in local, “great and powerful” words and what they are related to. Fundamental methodology is strongly believed in language universities. The translator is never sure that he knows a foreign language, he understands perfectly that the speech situations that arise are unpredictable. Reading in the classical way, students not only work with different lexical layers, but also learn to look at the world through the eyes of a “native speaker” - a native speaker.

The classical approach to the study of a foreign language, In this regard, the classical approach to the study of a foreign language has also changed somewhat, but the unique principles of the "classics" of Russian methods have been preserved. Sometimes they are actively used in schools of other methodological directions. The classic course is designed for students of all ages and often involves learning a language “from scratch”.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for the practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate their activity, creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the student's cognitive activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies such as collaborative learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources help to implement a person-centered approach to the learning process, individualization of teaching taking into account children's abilities, their level of learning

and provides differentiation. Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: vocabulary learning; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologue speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical phenomena.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The Global Internet provides students and teachers anywhere in the world with access to any information they need: regional geographic materials, news from the lives of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, and more.

A number of didactic problems can be solved in the classroom using the Internet in English: the formation of reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improving the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenish students' vocabulary; shaping students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work aims to explore the possibilities of Internet technology to broaden the horizons of school children, to establish and maintain business relationships and connections with their peers in English-speaking countries. Students are online tests, quizzes, competitions, participation in Olympiads, correspondence with peers in other countries, interviews, video conferences, etc. Students can learn about a problem they are currently working on in a project. The meaningful foundations of mass computerization are related to the fact that the modern computer is an effective means of optimizing mental working conditions, in general, any form of it. There is one peculiarity of the computer, which is determined by its use as a tool for teaching others and as an aid in the acquisition of knowledge, which is its lifelessness. The machine may have a "friendly" relationship with the user and sometimes "support" it, but it never shows signs of anger and does not allow you to feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is probably the most useful in individualizing certain aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is to form communicative competence, all other goals (upbringing, teaching, development) are realized in the process of achieving this main goal. The communicative approach involves the teaching of communication and the formation of the ability to interact across cultures, which is the basis of Internet activity. Beyond communication, the Internet makes no sense - it is an international multinational,

intercultural society whose lives are based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world who speak at the same time - it depends on the number and size of participants. The biggest conversation. To teach him a foreign language, we create a real model of communication. At present, priority is given to communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in a cultural context, autonomy of education and humanism. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as an integral part of communicative ability. The ultimate goal of foreign language teaching is to teach free orientation and the ability to respond adequately in a variety of situations in a foreign language environment, i. communication Today, new methods of using Internet resources are opposed to teaching traditional foreign languages. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that encourage material learning and develop adequate behavior (i.e., the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies, especially the Internet, are trying to fix this error. The communicative approach is to consciously understand the material and its methods of working with, a strategy that simulates communication aimed at creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. The communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only share information, but evaluate it. The main criterion that allows this approach to be distinguished from other types of learning activities is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their own opinions. The use of the Internet in a communicative approach is very well encouraged: its purpose is to motivate students to learn a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience. One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interactions in this lesson, which is commonly referred to as interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is “combining, coordinating, and complementing communicative goals and resulting efforts through the means of speech”. By teaching real language, the Internet helps to shape speaking skills and abilities, as well as provides a sincere interest and therefore efficiency in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity

not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond appropriately to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provides student-centered learning is the project approach as a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity, and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprosjects, collective, oral, explicit, written and Internet projects. In real practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects that are creative, practice-oriented, and have informative characters. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning that includes reading, listening, speaking, and grammar. The project method helps to develop students' active independent thinking and directs them to collaborative research. In my opinion, project-based teaching teaches children to collaborate, while learning to collaborate fosters moral values such as the ability to help and empathize, shapes creativity, and activates students. In general, there is an inseparability of teaching and learning in the project teaching process.

The project method develops students' communication skills, communication culture, the ability to form ideas concisely and easily, tolerance of the opinions of communication partners, the ability to obtain information from a variety of sources, modern reworked using computer technology, creating a language environment that contributes to the natural need in a foreign language. The project form of the work is one of the most up-to-date technologies that allow students to apply the accumulated knowledge on a topic. Students expand their horizons, the boundaries of language knowledge, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, understand each other in defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computers, and thus have the opportunity to communicate directly with the real language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom using only textbooks. Working on a project is a creative process. The student seeks a solution to the problem independently or under the guidance of a teacher, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual skills. In the process of foreign languages, the project method can be used within the framework of

program materials on almost any topic. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The introduction of information technology in education significantly diversifies the process of information perception and processing. Thanks to computers, the Internet, and multimedia, students have a unique opportunity to master large amounts of data with subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activities is also expanding significantly. In the context of the use of multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews and teleconferences. The main criterion for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in language portfolio technology is testing. The priority of this technology in education is to direct the process from teacher to student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his or her cognitive activities. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills of independent assimilation of information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

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